

1.+2. Request for onboarding and intake

📌 Introduction

In this page we describe the process of requesting data onboarding and our intake procedure.

For a quick overview see [🇬🇧 Metadata onboarding on the National Catalogue](#)

Steps 1-3 of the onboarding process

👤 Request for onboarding

To begin the onboarding process for the National Health Data Catalogue, we recommend first reviewing the documentation on this Wiki to understand the process. If you would like direct support to onboard metadata, please contact Health-RI via our service desk at servicedesk@health-ri.nl. A Health-RI representative will then reach out to schedule an initial meeting to discuss the process and any support needed.

You may also begin onboarding independently: [📄 3. Planning](#) and by mapping your metadata to the Health-RI metadata model and implementing or using a FAIR Data Point within your institute.

🇬🇧 Onboarding intake

If support is needed for the onboarding process, a Health-RI contact person will schedule an initial meeting to discuss the process and explore available options. During this meeting, we can also connect you with other onboarding projects at your institute or within your research field.

As part of the meeting, we will go through an intake form to understand what metadata is being onboarded and what infrastructure is available at your institute. This helps us assess the best solution for your situation.

✔ Next steps

If you do not require direct support or have had your intake, you can move to planning of onboarding [3. Planning](#) .

💬 Questions?

If you have questions about the onboarding process or would like to learn more. Reach out to our [Health-RI Servicedesk | Health-RI](#)

✉ servicedesk@health-ri.nl